

the unsprayed control plot as well as the surrounding plots, it produced no damage in any of the Phosvel-treated plots. ❧

Effects of soaking seeds in chemicals on the control of root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne graminicola*

K. S. Krishna Prasad and Y. S. Rao, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack-753006, India

Seeds of IR8 were soaked in a 4-ml test solution of each of 32 chemicals at doses of 500, 1,000, and 2,000 ppm for 12 and 24 h, or equivalent to doses of 0.2, 0.4, and 0.8 g/100 g seed with water control. Treated seeds were sown in soil inoculated with infective larvae of

M. graminicola. Nematicides and insecticides were effective to varying degrees in reducing the endoparasites and egg mass production. Among fungicides, only thiobendazole was effective (see table). Herbicides were phytotoxic; growth regulators and hormones were less effective; amino acids were ineffective. Oxamyl, fensulfothion, and phorate reduced endoparasites by more than 60% and egg masses by 80%. Carbofuran inhibited endoparasites, but was less effective in reducing egg mass production. Oxamyl at 500 and 1,000 ppm was as effective as other chemicals at higher doses either as 12- or 24-h seed-soak treatment. All herbicides affected seed viability and hormones, and growth regulators affected growth. ❧

Effects of soaking seeds in pesticides on invasion and development of *Meloidogyne graminicola*. Minimum nematode incidence at 2,000 ppm.

Treatment	Endoparasites (no.)	Egg masses (no.)	Germination (%)
<i>Nematicides and insecticides</i>			
Oxamyl	15.0	2.2	100
DBCP	23.1	5.5	100
Chlorpyrifos	18.0	6.1	100
Phorate	18.5	3.2	100
Carbofuran	30.2	3.2	100
Mephospholan	31.2	9.2	100
Fensulfothion	18.0	3.5	100
Quinalphos	25.1	7.1	95
<i>Fungicides</i>			
Mebenil	52.5	15.0	100
Bavistin	54.0	16.2	100
Thiabendazole	39.5	14.1	85
Cela - 50	50.0	16.5	92
Control	51.2	17.7	100

Whitebacked planthopper outbreak in Bangladesh

Shamsul Alam, entomologist; and M. Badiul Alam, scientific officer, Division of Entomology, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

The whitebacked planthopper *Sogatella furcifera* is a minor rice pest in Bangladesh. Two outbreaks of the pest were recorded in deep-water rice in 1963 (March–December and May–June). In 1967, the pest occurred in aus rice (March–August) and in deep-water rice during July in Comilla district. During the early 1970's, the pest was the

dominant hopper in the aus season in Mymensingh area, making up 61% of the total hopper population. But during the transplanted aman season (July–December), it ranked fourth and made up about 10% of the population.

In mid-April 1977, hopperbum due to *S. furcifera* was observed on the boro season crop (November–May) of IR8 in a patch of 55.74 sq m in the Mohammadpur area of Dacca. The crop was in the milky to dough stage; the plot was irrigated by sewage water. The population on 18 April was more than 1,000 adults and nymphs/hill. Loss was estimated at about 80% of the expected yield. ❧

Parasites of grasshopper eggs associated with paddy in Pakistan

Mohammad Irshad, pest management project, Agricultural Research Council, Islamabad, Pakistan

Scelio spp. are important parasites of grasshopper eggs. Six species parasitize grasshoppers that attack paddy in Pakistan. The widely distributed and adaptable parasites can withstand severely cold winters by hibernating as first-instar larvae in the host eggs. In summer the parasite adults are found mostly in shady places where they are protected from excessive heat; when dense vegetation is lacking, they creep into crevices.

Scelio do not parasitize all eggs in large egg pods, but egg pods with no more than 25 eggs are completely parasitized. Freshly laid host eggs are preferred to old ones.

The patchy distribution of host eggs may not allow enough of the parasites to develop to provide a high level of grasshopper control. Although *Scelio* do not seem to play a dominant role, they are in position to eliminate many eggs in the late fall. That could reduce the nymphal population in the spring and result in fewer adults in the summer. ❧

Subsequent infectivity of treated *Meloidogyne* larvae in chemicals

K. S. Krishna Prasad and Y. S. Rao, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack-753006, India

Larvae of *Meloidogyne graminicola* were held in aerated distilled water for 24 h after direct contact for 48 h with nematicides, insecticides, fungicides, herbicides, amino acids, growth regulators, and hormones at different levels. The contact toxicity tests showed that the following chemicals resulted in more than 90% mortality: oxamyl (nematicide) and propanil (herbicide) at 50 ppm and above; fensulfothion (insecticide) at 100 ppm; quinalphos (insecticide) and DBCP (nematicide) at 200 ppm; ZR-777 (hormone) at 500 ppm; and cycocel (growth regulator) at 1,000 ppm. DL forms of amino acids, fungicides, and other growth regulators were